

SPORTS TERMINOLOGY AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUISTIC RESEARCH

Yuan Xiaowei

National University of Uzbekistan, PhD student

Jining Normal University, Mongolia, China

E-mail: melinda1128@126.com

Tel: (998)948805817

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Abstract: As a relatively new branch of linguistics, sports terminology has been arouse more and more linguists' attention. This aricle is devoted to sports terminology as an object of linguistics research.

Key words: sports terminology, linguistics research, sports terms

The study of sports terminology is one of the most important problems in linguistics. In the course of the development of modern linguistic theory, the study of the functional characteristics of language units at different levels and the systematic relationship between them, the research and comparison of their semantic relations are among the most urgent issues of the modern science of language.

Sports terminology is a kind of language symbol, which belongs to the category of sports, and this language symbol has a specific concept, which can accurately describe the name of the sports event, theory, technical actions, tactics, competition rules, training methods, referee work or other related content , with text characteristics such as univocity, simplicity, common vocabulary with special meaning, professionalism, and systematicity.

Sports terminology has not yet been separated from the structure of scientific terminology and has not been studied linguistically and functionally.

Linguistic research of the term system of sports, defining the structure and semantic descriptions of terminological units used in this scientific field, as well as creating multilingual dictionaries of sports terms can help to overcome the difficulties that arise in the translation of special literature on sports.

The main issues of this problem were solved from the positions of the theory of derivation, and its essence is to describe language tools from the point of view of the system of concepts. The relevance of such an approach is based on its prognostic uncertainty, which is especially important in terms of regulation and standardization of individual terminological systems.

The need to develop each language terminologically is related to a number of extralinguistic and intralinguistic problems. In the language, each event, necessity, develops step by step due to the need to have its own means to express a fact. It is impossible to develop terminologies in the language of peoples who are not engaged in professional activities aimed at the goal, in an artificial and accelerated way. It makes no sense, because this process is not reflected in life. Before elucidating the level of study of sports-terms, we found it necessary to analyze the researches of scientists who contributed to the development of terminology in the field of science.

Term theory, the scope of meaning of sports-terms and issues of their development have been considered in the following centuries by Uzbek linguists.

Terminologist - scientist X.A. Dadabaev's thesis "Social-political and socio-economic terminology in monuments in the Turkish language of the 11-14th centuries" (1991), he researched the commercial and financial terminology in the texts written in the ancient

Turkic language. The author emphasized the languages of the peoples of Central Asia, because since ancient times, the caravan route connecting Southeast Europe, the Golden Horde, Iran, the Caucasus with Mongolia and China passed through this region, and trade played an important role in the life of the peoples of the region. The scientist states that "the presence of terms introduced from Turkish and Arabic-Persian languages in the monuments of the 11th-14th centuries may be related to this situation". Akcha "money", yarmak "copper coin, Chinese coin", dirnem "dirham", dinar, nakd, tetske "coin", bakyr "copper", altyn "gold", kemesh "silver" and explores other terms. It was evidenced that there was a wide trade based on monetary settlements during this period.

Another terminologist scientist D.Yu. Dosmukhamedov's dissertation entitled "General description of political economy terms in the modern Uzbek language and the main methods of their formation" is devoted to the study of economic terms in the Uzbek language.

In the process of the formation and development of political economy terms, the author identified four periods:

- 1) the period before the revolution, in which the terminology of political economy was composed of Arabism and Persianism (rent, institution "deal", tax, etc.);
- 2) 1917-1929, this period is characterized by criticizing the Arabisms in the language and replacing them with artificial terms (trading place "stock exchange", share document "share", etc.);
- 3) 1929-1945 years. During this period, the Uzbek language assimilates Russianism and Russian-international terminology;
- 4) from the post-war years to the present. This period is characterized by the development of terminology based on two sources - "internal resources of the Uzbek language and Russian-international terminology common to all nations".

Ch.S.Abdullaeva studied economic terms in a monographic way using Russian and Uzbek languages, while in her dissertation, Abdullaeva devoted to the comparative analysis of the lexicon of the field of international relations based on the Russian and Uzbek languages, P.P. Nishonov has carried out scientific works on the subject of comparative-typological research of legal terminology of French and Uzbek languages.

We can say that the study of sports lexicon belonging to Turkic languages started long ago. For example, the words related to sports were first expressed in sources related to geography written in the ancient Turkic language (remarks on the geographical, geological, biological, etc. conditions of this or that country were written). These ecowords are not classified into a separate lexeme category.

The interconnectedness of language and society, their dynamic and non-stop changes, as well as the widespread use of new terms and lexemes in the field of sports, require constant and consistent research in sports terminology.

References:

1. Liang Siyu. Research on the standardization of sports terminology in my country. Popular Sports, 2016, 6:145-146.

2. Paluanova Kh.D. Derivative semantic principles of ecological terms in English, Uzbek, Russian and Karakalpak languages. Philol. science. d-ri ... dis. autoref. - Tashkent, 2016. - 231 p.
3. Shi Xuanzhi. On the translation of sports terminology from the perspective of translation acceptability. Journal of Minjiang University, 2014, 3:35.

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